

APPLICATION OF AN AGENT APPROACH TO SIMULATION MODELING OF THE PROCESS OF EPIDEMIC SPREAD

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Abstract

One of the important applications of simulation modeling methods is forecasting the spread of epidemic diseases. System-dynamic and agent-based approaches are used in this area. The goal of agent-based modeling is to obtain an understanding of these global rules, the general behavior of the system, based on assumptions about the individual, private behavior of its individual active objects and the interaction of these objects in the system. System-dynamic and agent-based models of the spread of epidemic diseases have complementary properties, and therefore, the task of jointly using these classes of models to predict the dynamics of epidemic systems is relevant and requires a comprehensive comparison of their characteristics and properties.

Keywords: System-dynamic, Agent-based, Anylogic, Simulation modeling, Epidemic diseases.

System dynamics and agent-based modeling are two powerful tools used for forecasting the spread of epidemic diseases. Both approaches offer unique advantages and can be used in combination to provide comprehensive insights into the dynamics of disease transmission. System dynamics is a modeling approach that focuses on understanding the behavior of complex systems over time. It uses mathematical equations to represent the interactions and feedback loops between different components of the system. In the context of epidemic forecasting, system dynamics models can capture the dynamics of disease transmission by considering factors such as population size, birth and death rates, infection rates, recovery rates, and the impact of interventions or policies [1].

System dynamics models provide a holistic view of the disease spread by considering the interactions between different variables and their impact on the overall system behavior. These models can be used to simulate a range of scenarios and assess the effectiveness of various control strategies.

On the other hand, agent-based modeling focuses on representing the behavior and interactions of individual agents within a system. In the context of epidemic forecasting, agents can represent individuals or

groups of individuals with specific attributes and behaviors. Each agent follows a set of rules and can interact with other agents based on predefined conditions. By simulating the interactions between agents, agent-based models can capture the complex dynamics of disease transmission, including spatial heterogeneity, social networks, and individual-level behaviors [2].

Agent-based models offer a more detailed and granular representation of the system, allowing for the exploration of individual-level variations and the impact of localized interventions. These models can also capture the emergence of collective behaviors and patterns that may influence the spread of epidemics. By simulating a large number of agents, researchers can generate statistically significant results and gain insights into the potential outcomes of different intervention strategies. Combining system dynamics and agent-based modeling can provide a comprehensive and integrated approach to forecasting the spread of epidemic diseases [3, 4].

As an example, we considered two implementations of a simple SEIR model of the spread of an epidemic disease - influenza, in the Anylogic simulation environment. Figure 1 shows the structure of the system-dynamic SEIR model of influenza spread [5].

Figure 1. Structure of a system-dynamic model of epidemic spread

The SEIR model is a commonly used mathematical model for studying the spread of infectious diseases. It divides the population into four compartments: Susceptible (S), Exposed (E), Infected (I), and Recovered

(R). The model tracks the transitions between these compartments over time, providing insights into the dynamics of an epidemic. The parameters in the SEIR model are given in the Table 1.

Table 1

Description of model parameters	
Parameters	Description
Susceptible (S)	This compartment represents individuals who are susceptible to the disease and have not yet been infected.
Exposed (E)	This compartment represents individuals who have been exposed to the disease but are not yet infectious (in the incubation period).
Infected (I)	This compartment represents individuals who are infected and infectious.
Recovered (R)	This compartment represents individuals who have recovered from the disease and have developed immunity.
Infection_rate (β)	The proportion of infectious patients per unit of time among infected people
Emergence rate (μ)	The proportion of infected people per unit of time among susceptible people
N	Total number of people
c	The coefficient of human contact
e	The coefficient of contact with an infected person
i	The coefficient of contact with an infectious person
v	Probability of infection in the E-period
α	Probability of infection in the I-period
τ	Average Incubation Time
T	Average duration of illness

The dynamics of the model, the structure of which is presented in Figure 1, is described by the following system of algebraic-differential equations [6, 7]:

$$\frac{d(S)}{dt} = -\beta; \frac{d(E)}{dt} = \beta - \mu; \frac{d(I)}{dt} = \mu - \alpha; \frac{d(R)}{dt} = \alpha; \tag{1}$$

$$\beta = \frac{E}{N \times c \times (E \times e \times v + I \times i)}; \mu = \frac{E}{\tau}; \alpha = \frac{I}{T};$$

Initial values of the experiment parameters: N =1000; S = N – 1; E = 1; c = 5; e = 0.8; i = 0.25; v = 0.05; α =0.06; τ = 15; T = 15. At the beginning of the experiment, one person is infected. If a susceptible (S) person encounters an infected person (E), then he becomes infected with probability α. A person goes from the infected state (E) to the infectious state (I) after time τ, and after time T he goes to the healthy state (R) [8, 9]. The graph for the agent-based SEIR model of influenza is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Transition graph for the agent-based SEIR model of influenza spread

Figures 3 and 4 show the results of the experiment.

Figure 3. Results of the experiment with the SD model

Figure 4. Results of an experiment with an agent-based model

Thus, a comparative analysis of the static and dynamic characteristics of two implementations of the SEIR model of the spread of an epidemic disease - influenza - showed that with an increase in the number of agents, the behavior of the agent model approaches a similar system-dynamic one. However, at the same time, the requirements for computing power to support experiments with the model increase, which makes developments in the field of high-performance implementations of agent-based simulation models relevant.

Thus, system dynamics is an excellent tool for implementing simulation models for the spread of an epidemic disease. The model takes into account the process of removing infected subjects from a computer system. It is based on the assumption that during an epidemic, a certain number of infected subjects either get rid of the malware.

By isolating infected entities (excluding susceptible hosts from the network while the malware is spreading) and using more effective means of recovering infected entities, the infection curve can be flattened (resulting in a smaller peak in the number of infected individuals), and the latter method can also shorten the duration of the outbreak.

In summary, both system dynamics and agent-based modeling offer valuable tools for forecasting the spread of epidemic diseases. These approaches provide complementary insights into the dynamics of disease transmission and can be used in combination to enhance our understanding of the spread of epidemics and inform effective control strategies.

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